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Cause and effect – Boat traffic and declining water quality in Lake Wörthersee

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Carinthia, Austria, a popular holiday destination known for its clear water is currently facing a weakening of lake ecosystems, which is particularly evident in the bioindicator aquatic plants (macrophytes). Studies from 2021 show a significant decline in underwater plants and reeds, particularly in Lake Wörthersee, whose ecological status has dropped from “good” to “moderate” according to the European Union’s Water Framework Directive.

Boat waves are thought to be one of the main causes, along with factors such as intensive tourist use and climate change. The aim of the project WAMOS (WAve MOonitoring System based on Global Navigation Satellite System aided Inertial Navigation System (GNSS/INS) integration) is now to answer the question of whether and to what extent boat traffic influences macrophyte vegetation.

To investigate interactions between wave dynamics, sediment turbulence, and macrophytes in shore zones, we are developing a novel interdisciplinary monitoring system. A key innovation is the design and development of measuring buoys to record and quantify the incoming wave energy in near real-time. Wave heights are derived from inertial data recorded with low-cost micro-electro-mechanical system (MEMS) inertial measurement units (IMUs) and precise point positioning (PPP) positions based on correction data provided by the Galileo High Accuracy Service. A dedicated filtering algorithm was developed to distinguish boat-induced waves from natural wave patterns.

Initial field deployments at Lake Wörthersee demonstrate the system’s ability to capture fine-scale wave events relevant to ecological processes. We present the measurement setup, the methodology and preliminary results linking wave energy to biological indicators. This approach offers a cost-effective and scalable solution for monitoring wave impacts in lake ecosystems. By the end of the project in October 2025, findings will support evidence-based decision-making and environmental management at the national level.

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